

Acknowledgement

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Synthesis and Infrared Studies of Dioxouranium(VI) Chelates of 2-Ethoxycarbonyl-aminopyridine *N*-Oxide†

R. K. AGARWAL*, J. R. CHOPRA and S. C. RASTOGI

Department of Chemistry, Lajpat Rai College,
Sahibabad-201 005

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THE coordination chemistry of various oxocations is of interest because of the existence of a strong multiple metal-oxygen covalent bond persisting in various chemical environments. This can be employed as an internal molecular probe to understand more about the nature of metal-ligand bonds in the complexes of these ions¹. Cattalini *et al.*² have summarised various uranyl chelate complexes in a review article. But less is known about the uranyl chelates of aromatic amine *N*-oxides³. In the present communication we wish to report the chelates of uranyl(VI) with 2-ethoxycarbonylamino-pyridine *N*-oxide (ECAPO). The ligand ECAPO has three potential donor sites in tertiary amine *N*-oxygen, imino nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen. Zirconyl(IV) and thorium(IV) chelates of this ligand have already been reported^{4,5}.

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Experimental

Uranyl halides were prepared from nitrate while perchlorate was prepared as reported earlier⁶. The ligand ECAPO was prepared from 2-aminopyridine as reported earlier⁷.

The metal chelates were prepared by mixing the corresponding uranyl(VI) salt in methanol and 2,2'-dimethoxypropane (a dehydrating agent) and the ligand in anhydrous diethyl ether. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h. In each case the solid product obtained was filtered and washed with methanol and ether. All the chelates were dried *in vacuo* over P₂O₁₀.

All the physical measurements and analyses were performed as reported earlier⁶. Uranium was estimated as U₃O₈. The analytical data are presented in Table I.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data correspond to the compositions UO₂X₂.2ECAPO (X=Cl, Br, or NCS); UO₂(NO₃)₂.ECAPO and UO₂X₂.3ECAPO (X=ClO₄ or I). The molar conductance values of the chelates (in PhNO₂) indicate that chloro, bromo, thiocyanato and nitrate chelates are non-electrolytes, while the iodo and perchlorate chelates dissociate in PhNO₂ and behave as 1 : 2 electrolytes. Hence, in these cases all the anions are present outside the coordination sphere. The molecular weight determination also behaves in the similar way. The magnetic moments of the chelates indicate them to be diamagnetic.

Infrared study: The chelates are characterised on the basis of their ir spectra in 4000-200 cm⁻¹ region. Katritzky and Hands⁹ have examined the ir spectra of heterocyclic ring vibrations of large number of 2-substituted pyridine *N*-oxides. Partial use of their assignments as well as the reports of others¹⁰⁻¹² is made for the assignment of ir bands of ligand and in its metal chelates.

The four main absorption frequencies in ECAPO, namely urethane stretching, N-O stretching, N-O bending and C-H out-of-plane bending deformation are expected to be influenced on chelate formation.

In urethane stretching (R-NH-COOC₂H₅) the carbonyl absorption, responsible for the amide I band, is likely to be lowered. The amide I band in ECAPO appearing at 1730 cm⁻¹ is shifted to lower wave number after forming chelates, indicating a decrease in the stretching force constant of C=O as a consequence of coordination through the carbonyl oxygen atom of the free base. The NH stretching absorption in free ligand occurs at 3200 and 3120 cm⁻¹, which remains unaffected after complexation. This precludes the possibility of coordination through imine nitrogen atom.

TABLE I—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND SOME IMPORTANT IR FREQUENCIES OF URANYL(VI) CHELATES OF ECAPO

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)		
	U	Anion	N	O=O	N-O	U-O
ECAPO	—	—	—	1730 s	1220 s	—
UO ₂ Cl ₂ .2ECAPO	32.96 (33.75)	9.36 (10.07)	7.26 (7.94)	1680 s	1180 s	380 m
UO ₂ Br ₂ .2ECAPO	29.21 (29.97)	19.40 (20.15)	6.56 (7.05)	1690 s	1190 s	370 m
UO ₂ I ₂ .3ECAPO	21.90 (22.24)	22.10 (23.73)	7.36 (7.85)	1685 s	1190 s	365 m
UO ₂ (NCS) ₂ .2ECAPO	31.05 (31.73)	14.67 (15.46)	10.80 (11.20)	1680 s	1170 s	375 m
UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .ECAPO	40.63 (41.31)	—	9.20 (9.72)	1675 s	1175 s	365 m
UO ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂ .3ECAPO	22.98 (23.44)	18.20 (19.60)	7.36 (8.27)	1670 s	1180 s	360 m

The most important mode of vibration in the spectra of ECAPO is the one associated with N-O stretching. A band of very strong intensity at ~ 1220 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to this mode of vibration in the free ligand which undergoes a significant negative shift on chelation. The decrease in N-O stretching is attributed to coordination of the oxygen atom of the base to the metal ion^{4,8,13} exhibits a small shift in the spectra of the metal chelates as expected. Absorptions associated with CH out-of-plane deformation modes, as expected undergo a slight positive shift due to tightening of the aromatic ring on chelation^{4,8,13}. The overall ir spectral evidence suggests that ECAPO acts as a bidentate ligand and coordinates through N-oxygen and carbonyl oxygen atoms forming a seven-membered chelate ring. The band observed in the 400-300 cm⁻¹ region is assigned to U-O vibrations.

The oxocation band (U=O) in all the chelates has been assigned at ~ 960 and 920 cm⁻¹ as asymmetric and symmetric frequencies¹³⁻¹⁵.

The band ~ 260 cm⁻¹ in chloro chelate has been assigned as U-Cl linkage¹³. The strong ν_3 and ν_4 bands in the spectra of perchlorate chelate occur unsplit at ~ 1085 and 620 cm⁻¹, respectively indicating the ionic nature of the perchlorate groups¹³⁻¹⁵. In nitrate chelate the absence of ionic band at ~ 1360 cm⁻¹ and presence of ν_1 and ν_4 bands at 1280 and 1520 cm⁻¹ clearly indicate the covalent nature of nitrate groups. The nitrate groups seem to be bidentate in this chelate since the ir frequencies due to this group occur in almost the same frequency ranges ($1520, 1280, 1030, 800,$ and 730 cm⁻¹ as $\nu_4, \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_6,$ and ν_3/ν_5 , respectively) as in UO₂(NO₃)₂.2H₂O¹⁶. In thiocyanato chelate the bands at 2080 and 820 cm⁻¹ are due to ν_{C-N} and ν_{C-S} strongly suggesting N-bonded NCS¹⁷.

In conclusion the equatorial coordination number of uranium in these chelates is found to be six.

Thermal study: The thermal investigations of uranyl(VI) complexes of aromatic amine N-oxides have been carried out to a limited extent. Ramamurthy and Patel⁶ reported uranyl(VI) perchlorate complex of pyridine N-oxide by DTA. Agarwal *et al.*¹³ have also reported DTA results on some uranyl(VI) chelates of aromatic amine N-oxides. In the present work DTA of some uranyl(VI) chelates of ECAPO are reported. The curves indicate the

absence of water molecules either inside or outside the coordination sphere. Halo and nitrate complexes decompose endothermically while perchlorate complex decomposes with exo peak. Finally, a broad peak is due to metal oxidation. These changes can be shown as

On the basis of decomposition temperature the thermal stability of these chelates is in the order,

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Synthesis and Characterisation of Mixed Heteropoly Molybdotungstotellurate

S. K. ROY

Department of Chemistry, Ranchi University, Ranchi-834 008

B. N. GHOSH

Department of Chemistry, Gossner College, Ranchi-834 001

and

A. K. CHAKRABORTY

Central Fuel Research Institute, Ranchi

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accepted 15 February 1985

SYNTHESIS of ammonium salts as well as free acids of the 6-heteropoly anion^{1,2} of general formula $[\text{NiMo}_{6-n}\text{W}_n\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_6]^{4-}$ and some mixed 12-heteropoly anions, involving successive replacement by pentavalent vanadium in molybdophosphoric acid has been reported by Tsigdinos *et al.*³. Solution phase studies of this class of compounds have been done exhaustively by Spitsyn *et al.*⁴. Niobium, like vanadium can also replace molybdenum in the heteropoly anion $[\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]^{3-}$. A molybdovanadoselenious acid of composition $\text{H}_6[\text{SeMo}_{10}\text{V}_2\text{O}_{40}]\cdot\text{X}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been prepared by etheral extract and partially characterised⁵. Heteropoly anion of general formula $[\text{XZW}_{11}\text{O}_{40}\text{H}_2]^{2-}$, where X=Si, Ge or P and Z=Co^{II}, Co^{III} or Ni^{II} have been prepared⁶. In view of these reports, it appeared worthwhile to investigate the replacement of molybdenum by tungsten in 6-heteropoly molybdotellurate anion $[\text{TeMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$, which is well characterised^{7,8}.

Experimental

Solutions of K_2WO_4 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{WO}_4$ were prepared from $\text{WO}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ using KOH and NH_4OH , respectively. Complete and stoichiometric reaction was determined by absence of precipitate and a final pH of ~8.

Sodium 5-molybdo 1-tungstotellurate: A homogeneous aqueous solution of 400 ml of molybdic acid was prepared by dissolving 9.90 g $\text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 100 ml water by heating for 5 to 6 h at 80° with occasional stirring. To that hot solution an aqueous solution of 100 ml $\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.30 g) were added gradually with stirring followed by addition of 100 ml solution of NaNO_3 (3.06 g). The pH of the solution was adjusted at 2.5 to 3.5 by adding 12 ml glacial acetic acid. It was refluxed for 3 h at 90°.

The volume of the total solution was reduced to 100 ml and left for crystallisation. After 10 days, bright glassy crystals were collected, recrystallised from hot water and washed with 90% ethanol to yield the product (70%) (Found: Na, 8.50; Te, 7.5; W, 11.36; Mo, 29.86; H_2O , 17.90. $\text{Na}_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. Na, 8.61; Te, 7.99; W, 11.48; Mo, 29.96; H_2O , 17.97%).

Potassium 5-molybdo 1-tungstotellurate: Synthesis was carried out as above by substituting potassium tungstate for sodium tungstate. Large glassy prismatic crystals obtained after 12 days of studying were recrystallised from hot water and washed with 95% ethanol to yield the product (95%) (Found: K, 14.26; Te, 7.73; W, 11.20; Mo, 29.44; H_2O , 13.19. $\text{K}_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. K, 14.39; Te, 7.87; W, 11.31; Mo, 29.52; H_2O , 13.28%).

Ammonium 5-molybdo 1-tungstotellurate: Using ammonium tungstate in place of sodium tungstate and following the same procedure for preparation as above, large glassy crystals of the compound were collected after 9 days (70%) (Found: N, 4.91; Te, 7.50; W, 10.83; Mo, 28.46; H_2O , 23.46. $(\text{NH}_4)_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 22\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. N, 5.00; Te, 7.61; W, 10.95; Mo, 28.57; H_2O , 23.57%).

The percentage of water in the compounds was determined by heating the samples around 500° to constant weight. Sodium and potassium were estimated⁹ by zinc uranyl acetate and tetraphenyl borate methods, respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by elemental analysis. Molybdenum and tungsten were estimated⁹ by precipitating out simultaneously with α -benzoinoxime. Tellurium was estimated gravimetrically⁹ as elementary tellurium by reducing it with sodium-hypophosphite.

Infrared spectra: The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Peaks at 3350 to 3450 and 1610 to 1630 cm^{-1} regions are for lattice water¹⁰. Other peaks are at 320 to 325 and 685 to 690 cm^{-1} for Te-O in octahedral co-ordination¹¹, 900-1000 cm^{-1} due to M-O and 725-850 cm^{-1} for M-O-M (M=Mo or W) bridging².

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of $\text{K}_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in solutions at pH 2.5 and 5 were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 202 spectrophotometer. The intense absorption at 260 nm may be due to charge transfer from oxygen to molybdenum (or tungsten), as shown by heteropolytungstate, in the uv region¹².

Thermal stability: The studies on thermal stability of these heteropoly compounds were conducted by TGA, DTA and by heating at fixed temperature followed by solubility determinations of the heated materials to ascertain decomposition. All the experiments were carried out under nitrogen at a heating rate of 5° min^{-1} . Replacement of one of the six MoO_6 octahedra by a WO_6 octahedron in the heteropoly anion $[\text{TeMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$ does not lead to any significant change in the thermal